

Halide-catalysed Reduction of Heptavalent Manganese by Some Dicarboxylic Acid Anions

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The mechanism of the reduction of heptavalent manganese by malonate and oxalate, catalysed by halides in the order: $I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$, is accounted for by postulating the intermediate formation of atomic halogen and the relevant organic free radical in a chain process. The chain is set in by the action of MnO_4^{1-} on halide, resulting in the formation of atomic halogen and Mn(VI). The kinetics of the catalysed oxidation is in agreement with the proposed mechanism. Rate data reveal the dominant nature of manganese(II) over the organic anion in the competition for the higher-valent manganese even at lower manganese(II) concentration.

The reaction of permanganate with halides is postulated to proceed through the step:

and subsequent formation of lower-valent manganese by a single-electron transfer till Mn(VI) is reduced to Mn(II). In presence of an oxidisable species, the atomic halogen may oxidise it, giving rise to the relevant organic free radical, and thus may induce oxidation of organic substances. This has been confirmed by the induced reduction of heptavalent manganese by malonate and oxalate in presence of halides in the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were of AnalaR or equivalent specifications. Potassium permanganate solution was filtered through a sintered glass crucible before standardization by the oxalate [method]. Malonate-malonic and oxalate-oxalic acid mixtures of varying pH, measured with a Radio pH-meter-4 of reproducibility ± 0.001 pH, were obtained by putting in the requisite quantity of KOH.

A requisite quantity of the oxidant was introduced into known amounts of the reductant and the halide and the kinetics was followed by estimating the concentrations of the oxidant iodometrically at definite time lags.

DISCUSSION

The reduction of permanganate by malonate and oxalate by itself is accompanied by long induction periods of the order of hours at relatively low acidity. Introduction of halides in sufficient concentrations initiates and enhances the reduction in the order:

$\text{Cl}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{I}^-$. The rate of reduction does not conform to the usual kinetics, but it obeys an autocatalytic rate expression¹ with reasonable regularity. It should be emphasised that the constants are unusually high in the initial stage of the reaction (Tables IA and IB).

TABLE IA

$$\text{Validity of the rate expression } K = \frac{2.303}{t \times 60(a+b)} \log_{10} \frac{a(b+x)}{b(a-x)}$$

(Malonic acid) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. (NaHCO_3) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$.
(Iodide) = $10 \times 10^{-3}N$. pH = 2.54. Temp. = 24°.

<i>t</i> (min.) ..	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹) ..	4.07	3.42	3.10	2.68	2.75	2.74	2.84	2.71

TABLE IB

(Oxalic acid) = $1 \times 10^{-2}N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. (NaHCO_3) = $0.8 \times 10^{-2}N$.
(Iodide) = $3 \times 10^{-3}N$. pH = 4.40. Temp. = 28°.

<i>t</i> (min.) ..	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹) ..	6.06	4.85	4.07	3.65	3.28	3.16	3.33	3.04	3.11	2.98

When the pink colour is completely discharged, a first-order decomposition of the manganic complex proceeds.

TABLE II

Effect of acidity and conc. of the halide on the rate of reduction.

A. Malonic acid. (Reductant) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. Temp. = 24°.				B. Oxalic acid. (Reductant) = $1 \times 10^{-2}N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. Temp. = 28°.			
pH.	(Iodide) × 10 ³ N			pH.	(Iodide) × 10 ³ N.		
	15.	10.	5.		2.	3.	4.
	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹				<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹		
2.54	3.44	2.75	1.71	4.78	2.35	2.03	3.89
2.72	2.91	2.17	1.49	4.40	2.70	3.13	4.51
2.95	2.16	1.86	1.32	4.02	3.76	5.01	..

In presence of an equivalent amount of manganese (II) that might be formed during the oxidation of halide, the rate constant was found to be $5.41 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at (malonic acid) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$, (NaHCO_3) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$, pH = 2.54, (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$, (MnSO_4) = $15 \times 10^{-3}N$, and temp. = 24° and $1.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at (oxalic acid) = $1 \times 10^{-2}N$, (NaHCO_3) = $0.8 \times 10^{-2}N$, pH = 4.40, (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$, (MnSO_4) = $2 \times 10^{-2}N$, and temp. = 28°, which are many times less than the corresponding values in presence of halides. Obviously, manganese (II) does not solely account for the enhanced rate.

Studies on the impact of halogens on these reductions reveal that aqueous iodine induces the above reductions with a very high induction factor and provides quantitatively the same result as that of an equivalent amount of iodide. The same is not found to be true with bromine and more so with chlorine though bromide and chloride at higher concentrations do enhance the reduction. When halogens are present, the chain initiation can be ascribed to the interaction of the halogen and the organic substrate, as shown below:

and this reaction will be prominent in the following order: $Cl_2 > Br_2 > I_2$. Hence the rate of the induced reduction too should be expected in the same order. But from the reverse experimental finding: $I_2 > Br_2 > Cl_2$, we have to conclude that the initiation by step (2) is not important and also that the subsequent chain-breaking reaction (21) is more prominent for chlorine and bromine than for iodine: $I_2 < Br_2 < Cl_2$, though step (21) is not so predominant as to completely suppress the enhanced reduction in the case of oxalate, which emerges from the fact that higher concentrations of chloride and bromide considerably catalyse the reduction of permanganate by oxalate.

That the rate of enhanced reduction depends on the concentration of halide and acidity (Table II) is suggestive of the chain being set in by the action of MnO_4^{1-} on the halide also in addition to the usual process involving manganese (II), which generates Mn (VI), and atomic halogen in the system (cf. reaction 1).

The catalytic efficiency of the halides on these reduction is in the order: $I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$, which is in fact consistent with the above chain-initiation process.

The oxidation of oxalate or malonate by permanganate is capable of reducing mercuric chloride and initiating polymerisation and thereby shows the intermediate formation of some organic free radical. Abel² suggested this active species to be $C_2O_4^{1-}$ for oxalate. Malaprade and Coulombeau³ have recently reiterated this suggestion. Taube *et al.*⁴ also concur with this view. Drummond and Waters⁵ suggested the probable formation of $\cdot HC(COOH)_2$ as an active entity in the oxidation of malonic acid by Mn(III).

Atomic halogen, thus formed in reaction(1), derives the relevant organic free radical from the organic substrate:

and Mn(VI) brings about a reaction sequence as:

2. *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, 43, 629.

3. *Compt. rend.*, 1954, 238, 2322.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1418; Wolsz, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 21, 198; Kalra and Ghosh, Doctoral Thesis, Allahabad University, 1962.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2457.

The organic free radicals, thus produced in proportion to the higher-valent manganese species, initiate further reduction of heptavalent manganese in a rate-limiting electron-transfer from the organic free radical to the permanganate anion.

Thus there is the perpetuation of the chain. The reactions:

also make a major contribution to this effect.

The absence of an explosive chain reveals the loss of the active species in reactions:

Manganese (II) formed in the system initiates further chain by the reaction:

and thus brings out a dominant autocatalytic character. The fall in autocatalytic constants with the progressive formation of Mn(II) in the system suggests the gradual domination of the reactions:

over those of (4-6). This predominance of the reactions (16-18) decreases the stationary concentration of the active transient entity $\cdot R^{1-}$ for the dismutation of the manganic complex to yield the species $\cdot R^{1-}$ being comparatively a slow process. This should obviously result in a fall of the rate constant, as is found to be the case.

Additional evidence in support of this mechanism can be had from the chain-termination reactions:

which is dependent on the relation⁶:

$$\frac{(X)}{(\cdot R^{1-})} = \frac{K_2(X_2)}{K_3(R^{2-})} \frac{V_3}{V_2} = \frac{f_2 Z_2}{f_3 Z_3} \frac{(X_2)}{(R^{2-})} \exp. (E_2 - E_3)/RT$$

It follows that when V_3 is slow as compared to V_2 at a high $(X_a)/(R^{2-})$ ratio, the stationary concentration of (X) is high and hence the loss of the atomic halogen by association among themselves is large. This is found to be true in the reduction of permanganate by tartrate and citrate in presence of iodide where the reaction between these organic anions and atomic iodine is comparatively slow and consequently catalytic phenomenon is not significant enough.

Further at low $(X_a)/(R^{2-})$ ratio and V_3 sufficiently fast, the chief chain-breaking step is reaction (21). This reaction is expected to be most predominant in the case of the chloride-catalysed reduction of permanganate by malonate in the series investigated here and as expected, the catalysed reduction is found to be insignificant in this instance.

Incidentally, Taube⁷ observed a 20% increase in the rate of decomposition of manganic oxalate when chloride concentration was changed from nil to 2*N* in the determination of the dissociation constants of the complexes of manganese (III). The limiting Bronsted equation predicts no variation of specific rate with ionic strength for a reaction of this type. The values of the dissociation constants evaluated by him need to be revised for higher concentrations of chloride being a catalyst in the disproportionation of these complexes.

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